

Academic Study That Symptoms of Dissociative Identity Disorder (DID) Can Be So Significant That They Cause Suffering Not Only For The Affected Person, But Also For His Family, Friends, And The Broader Community

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To cite this article: Çağlar Seziş, Science, Volume 4, No. 11-2, 2022, p. 40 – 59. - 0099-0001-2211-0302.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

Dissociative Identity Disorder, commonly known as DID, is characterized by a disruption of an individual's identity due to the presence of two or more identities that exist and have the potential to take control of the person, also known as personality states. Signs of this condition are changes in behavior, awareness, memory, perception, cognition, and/or sensory-motor functioning, as well as a keen sense of spontaneous dissociation and agency. It is possible for the person to experience recurrent memory loss about normal, daily events, important personal information, and/or traumatic experiences (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). The symptoms of dissociative

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identity disorder (DID) can be significant enough to cause suffering not only for the person affected, but also for their family, friends, and the wider community. Comorbid conditions such as helplessness, anxiety, drug use, self-harm and non-epileptic seizures are outcomes; moreover, seventy percent of outpatients tried suicide multiple times in addition to self-harm (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). They may suffer from deficits in awareness and forgetfulness, unaware that they may be suffering from dissociative identity disorder (DID), an unknown disease. This may be because they are not aware of their condition. There is a debate as to whether dissociative identity disorder (DID) is a real condition, and there is also a debate as to why it occurs. Media presented DID; however, the way it is presented is not always correct and may prove to be just a media gimmick to grab the public's attention and make the issue more captivating. According to Robert T. Muller (2013), fiction tends to overgeneralize and exaggerate the situation, giving the public a false impression and concept that the disorder exists, and that the diagnosis is incorrect. For example, in films such as Raising Cain (1992), Fight Club (1999), Secret Window (2004), the main character gradually transforms into someone with a more sinister mindset to achieve their most sinister goals.

Keywords: *DID, Dissociative Identity Disorder, Human Psychology, Psychological Disorders*

1. Introduction

Most people who struggle with DID do not develop what is known as a "bad alter" (Muller, 2013). One of the things to consider is how to aid a person whose problem or solution is currently unavailable.

This literature review will focus on examining four topics:

- (1) *prevalence and presence of DID.*
- (2) *How it develops.*
- (3) *available treatments and*
- (4) *Guidelines for future research.*

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Considering the burden of the disorder and the misconceptions presented by the media, we will focus on examining these four issues. For decades, people have debated whether dissociative identity disorder (DID) really is a condition. The American Psychiatric Association estimates the prevalence of dissociative identity disorder (DID) among adults in the United States to be 1.5%; 1.6% of this number is men and 1.4% is women. Researchers Sar, Önder, Kılınçslan, Zoroğlu, and Alyanak (2014) conducted a study on 116 adolescents (11-17 years old) receiving outpatient psychiatric treatment in Turkey. They discovered that 33 (45.2%) of the seventy-three participants had dissociative disorder, 12 (16.4%) had DID, and 21 (28.8%) had dissociative disorder not otherwise specified. The research was conducted in Turkey. Another study was conducted in Puerto Rico and found that 4.9% of the youth there showed signs of pathological dissociation. Another study in Sweden found that 2.3% of nonclinical adolescents and 50% of clinical adolescents had dissociative symptoms . According to these figures, dissociative identity disorder (DID) may not be as rare or nonexistent as previously believed and may be more common among adolescents than adults. It is natural for a person to go through a process known as an "identity crisis" when they are a teenager, making it one of the hurdles to overcome when screening teens for dissociative disorders. Therefore, it will come to the fore more in those years; however, they may later discover that this is not the real DID and they have misdiagnosed it.

2. How It Evolves Over Time

There is an ongoing debate about the factors that contribute to the development of DID. While one school of thought argues that it results from traumatic experiences such as sustained childhood neglect or physical and/or sexual abuse, another school of thought claims that dissociative identity disorder is fantasy-based or, in other words, promoted by high suggestibility, fantasy disposition, and sociocultural influences. Vissia et al., 2016). Another school of thought argues that Dissociative Identity Disorder is not a unique disorder, but a hallmark of Borderline Personality Disorder (SPD) (Suetanie & Markwick, 2014).

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According to the Trauma Model, Dissociative Identity Disorder (DID) occurs with traumatic events, most of which occur in childhood. The way parents raise and interact with their children, and the quality of the bond that exists between parents, have a significant impact on a child's development. Research has shown that growing up and living in an abusive and negligent environment can interfere with a person's ability to integrate, self-regulate, and build a sense of trust and security. In severe circumstances, it can even change a person's feeling of who they are as an individual. It is considered "escape when there is no escape," and in extreme cases, abuse victims gain DID.

Dissociative identity disorder (DID) is the first line of defense used by the victim when defending himself against abuse (Baker, 2010). According to Baker (2010), dissociative identity disorder (DID) is a disorder of under-expression of a single personality, not a condition of several personalities. Personalities appear because of traumatic situations that occur in patients' lives, because of an effort to help patients and to help them cope with the consequences of such experiences. A study was conducted of delinquent teenagers suffering from dissociative disorders, and researchers found that 96.8% of them had a history of trauma . This has led researchers to question whether traumatic experiences play a key role in the development of IPD (Sa et al., 2014). Abused patients often show symptoms such as post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), panic disorder, agoraphobia, social and simple phobia, significant depression, and drug abuse (Ellason, Ross & Fuchs, 1996). Numerous studies have been conducted to decide whether the Trauma Model is correct. One of these studies, the case study conducted by Baker, is one of the studies that highlights this model (2010). One patient Baker dealt with, Jackie had suffered severe childhood trauma , including sexual, physical, and emotional abuse . Baker was helping Jackie survive her ordeal. Jackie coped with each painful event by developing a new alter ego for herself, eventually deceiving herself into believing that the dreadful events really happened to her alter ego and not hers. Baker (2010) collaborated with herself and one of her alter personalities to help her understand that her trauma was real and that she had to accept that it happened on her own to move on with her life.

3. Fantasy Model

The Fantasy Model is the other model that tries to explain why some people may develop DID. According to this model, dissociative identity disorder (DID) is a sociocognitive or non-traumatic model and is associated with resuscitation, sleep disturbances, suggestive psychotherapy, and/or sociocultural factors. Additionally, this model classifies DID as a non-trauma related model. One of the limitations of this model is that healthy people can mimic some of the most obvious and well-known symptoms of ICD, such as psychoform dissociation, amnesia, loss of control, and definition confusion. However, these healthy people do not show the subtle and lesser-known symptoms of DID, which, according to the American Psychiatric Association (2013), tends to be accompanied by depression, anxiety, substance abuse, self-harm, or non-depression.

In addition, some structures of the two models can be combined. Traumatic dissociative phenomena and fantasy dissociative phenomena are not two distinct categories of dissociative experiences; For example, traumatized people will use fantasy as a coping mechanism to deal with traumatic events and the consequences of trauma (Vissia et al., 2016). Sybil's case can serve as a case study to help explain the Fantasy Model. This case involves a woman with sixteen different personalities who, with the help of her psychiatrist and after a while, through the integration of her various alter egos, begins to lead a normal life. Rieber (1999) conducted case study to explore how hypnosis, false memories, and DID are linked. The psychotherapist responsible for Sybil's treatment concluded that Wilbur had convinced Sybil that she had several personalities that she did not actually have.

Since these two models are the best known, Vissia et al. (2016) conducted a study in which they compared individuals with dissociative identity disorder (DID), post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), individuals simulating IPD, and healthy participants. The purpose of the study was to decide which model was more correct. They divided the individuals into two groups and had them fill out self-report questionnaires so they could assess traits related to traumatic experiences and imagery. Individuals with DID score highest on trauma measures and, contrary to widespread belief, were not more prone to fantasy or suggestibility, and were not more prone to concocting memories. The results of this experiment supported DID's Trauma Model, but the Fantasy Model's

results contradicted his theory. The final theory about what causes DID is that it is a serious manifestation of borderline personality disorder (BPD). The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders defines borderline personality disorder as "a pervasive pattern of instability and significant impulsivity in interpersonal connections, self-image, and emotions" (American Psychiatric Association, 2013, p.663).

Patients with borderline personality disorder, including, but not limited to, an unhealthy fear of abandonment, which may be real or imaginary; an unstable pattern of interpersonal relationships; impulsivity in at least two areas that can harm them ; and other symptoms are included. Dissociative identity disorder (DID) is hypothesized to be one of the symptoms of borderline personality disorder (BPD), which is also characterized by identity disruption and transient, stress-related paranoid thinking or severe dissociative symptoms . Laddis, Dell, and Korzekwa (2017) conducted a study in which they examined the processes behind dissociation, as well as symptoms of dissociative identity disorder (DID) and borderline personality disorder (BPD) . During the study, there were a total of one hundred people identified with BPD and seventy-five patients diagnosed with IPD. The primary symptoms of patients with DID (presence of changes, identity confusion, and memory problems) and patients with BPD (flashbacks, identity confusion, and memory problems) were comparable, but these symptoms were believed to be elicited by separate sets. While second identities occur most of the time, but not always, in patients with DID, only 24 percent of individuals with BPD showed dissociative episodes of alter origin. According to the findings of the study, the fact that these two conditions have some common symptoms does not mean that they are the same problem. Since each has its own unique symptoms and characteristics, it should be considered its own condition. Increasing clinical recognition of dissociative conditions, the publication of many research studies and scientific studies on the subject, and the development of specialized diagnostic tools have contributed to improved diagnosis, assessment, and treatment of dissociative disorders over the past 30 years.

United States, Canada, Puerto Rico, Argentina, Netherlands, Norway, Switzerland, Northern Ireland, Great Britain, France, Germany, Italy, France, Sweden, Spain, Turkey, Israel, Oman, Iran, India, Australia, New Zealand Philippines Uganda, China, and Japan are just a few of the countries

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that have contributed to the international literature on dissociative disorders. Peer-reviewed publications by clinicians and researchers in at least twenty-six countries, including the United States and Canada, have appeared in the international literature . These publications include clinical case series and case reports.

1. *Research on psychophysiological, neurobiological and neuroimaging processes.*
2. *A discussion of the development of diagnostic tools.*
3. *Descriptions of open clinical trials and treatment outcome studies.*
4. *And explanations of treatment, treatment modalities, and treatment dilemmas.*

They provide evidence that IPD is a valid cross-cultural diagnosis with validity comparable to or exceeding other accepted psychiatric diagnoses (Gleaves, May, & Cardea, 2001). This evidence has been presented consistently. Cardea, Van Duijl, Weiner, and Terhune (2009) state that these researchers state that pathological changes in identity and/or consciousness may manifest themselves as having a soul in other cultures and as syndromes related to other cultures . The DID Diagnostic and Treatment Guidelines present key findings and accepted principles that reflect current scientific knowledge and clinical experience specific to the diagnosis and treatment of DID and similar forms of DDNOS. These findings and principles are specific to the diagnosis and treatment of DID and similar forms of DDNOS.

It is important to note that the information contained in the Guidelines is intended to complement rather than replace accepted principles of psychotherapy and other related fields.

The treatment of DID should be based on the basic principles of psychotherapy and its medical management. Additionally, therapists should only use special techniques when necessary to address certain dissociative symptoms. It is not the intent of the authors of the Clinical Practice Guidelines that their recommendations be interpreted or used in any way as a standard of clinical care. The best practice recommendations currently reflect the latest scientific findings in this area. The Guidelines are not intended to be comprehensive in covering proper treatment pathways or to exclude the possibility of using any other proper treatment. Also, even if you adhere strictly to the Guidelines, there is no guarantee that your patient will respond positively to treatment. Treatment

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should always be individualized, and clinicians should use professional judgment to decide whether a particular form of care is proper for a particular patient considering the clinical data presented by the patient and the options available at the time of treatment.

5. Epidemiology, Clinical Diagnosis and Diagnostic Procedures

Both dissociative identity disorder and dissociative disorders are not uncommon problems. According to studies conducted on the general population, the prevalence rate of dissociative identity disorder varies between 1% and 3% of the population (Johnson, Cohen, Kâsen, & Brook, 2006; Murphy, 1994; Ross, 1991; 'Sar, Akyüz , & Doğan) , 2007; Waller & Ross, 1997) (Johnson, Cohen, Kasen & Brook, 2006; Ross, 1991; Waller & Ross, 1997). Overall, 1% to 5% of patients hospitalized in general psychiatry units; in adolescent inpatient units; and may meet the diagnostic criteria for obsessive-compulsive disorder in programs that treat substance abuse, eating disorders, and obsessive -compulsive disorder. These findings come from clinical studies conducted in North America, Europe, and Turkey. Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition, Text Revision (DSM–IV–TR); American Psychiatric Association, 2000a) diagnostic criteria for dissociative identity disorder (DID), especially when evaluated with structured diagnostic tools (Bliss & Jeppsen, 1985; Foote, Smolin, Kaplan, Legatt, & Lipschitz, 2006; Goff, Olin, Jenike, Baer, & Buttolph, 1992) ; Johnson e A significant proportion of the patients participating in these studies had not been previously diagnosed with a clinical diagnosis of dissociative disorder An accurate clinical diagnosis enables prompt initiation of treatment for dissociative disorders Primary causes of difficulties in trying to diagnose ICD are dissociation, dissociative disorders and psychological trauma as well as prejudice Therefore, there is no clinical suspicion about dissociative disorders and this leads to misunderstandings.

Most medical professionals have been led to believe (or instructed to assume) that dissociative identity disorder is an extremely rare condition characterized by exaggerated and dramatic symptoms .

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According to research conducted by RP Kluft (2009), although DID is quite common (p. six hundred), "only 6% make their DID permanently visible". RP Kluft (1991) used the term "diagnostic windows" to describe these brief glimpses of the situation at hand (also discussed by Loewenstein, 1991a). A typical patient with dissociative identity disorder (DID) displays a polysymptomatic mix of dissociative and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms embedded in a matrix of unrelated trauma. This is done instead of showing visibly different alternative identities (e.g., depression, panic attacks, substance abuse, somatoform symptoms, eating disorder symptoms). Because of the prevalence of these newer and well-known symptoms, doctors can sometimes only find concomitant diseases themselves. When this occurs, the individual suffering from DID who has not yet received a diagnosis may be subject to prolonged and often inconclusive treatment for other disorders.

Finally, all medical professionals conduct diagnostic interviews and mental status assessments by protocols they are instructed to practice throughout their professional training. Unfortunately, these traditional interviews often do not include any questions about resolution, PTSD symptoms, or a history of psychological trauma. Because dissociative identity disorder (DID) patients rarely supply information about their dissociative symptoms voluntarily, it is difficult for a physician to diagnose dissociative identity disorder (DID) in the absence of focused questioning about dissociation. In addition, most doctors have little or no training in dissociation and DID, so they have trouble finding the signs and symptoms of DID even if they occur on their own. This is true even when symptoms are present. The doctor has no choice but to question the patient's dissociative symptoms to make a diagnosis of dissociative identity disorder (DID). When considered necessary, the clinician's interview should be supplemented with screening tools and structured interviews that assess the presence or absence of dissociative symptoms and dissociative disorders. Terminology and Definitions of Dissociation Both the American Psychiatric Association (2000a) and the World Health Organization (1992) have classified dissociative diseases; however, none of these organizations have accurately described the nature of the divergence. Considering this, the DSM-IV-TR states that "The essential feature of Dissociative Disorders is a disturbance in the generally integrated processes of consciousness, memory,

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identity, or perception" (American Psychiatric Association, 2000a, p. 519). There is considerable disagreement as to whether the concept of segregation should be too broad or too narrow .

6. Dissociation Process

According to Putnam (1989), the dissociation process can be seen as "a natural process that is first used defensively by the person to overcome traumatic events that turn into a maladaptive or pathological process over time". Many authors, such as Cardea (1994) and Holmes et al., have used the term descriptively to refer to changes in consciousness characterized by a sense of self-detachment and/or self-detachment, as well as failures to integrate knowledge and self-attributions that should normally be integrated . Pierre Janet's distinction between dissociative negative (i.e., reduction or elimination of a psychological process) and positive dissociative (i.e., occurrence or increase of a psychological process) symptoms supplies a further subcategory of the disorder. In their definition, Dell, and O'Neil (2009) supplied more detail on the basic idea of degradation introduced in DSM-IV:

- *The most important symptom of pathological dissociation is the partial or complete disruption of the normal integration of a part (psychological functioning of the person).*

more specific , dissociation can unexpectedly interrupt, alter, or interfere with a person's consciousness and experience of their body, world, self, mind, mediation, intentionality, thinking, believing, knowing, recognizing, remembering:

- *To feel, to desire, to speak, to act, to see, to hear, etc. hearing, smelling, tasting, touching, etc.*
- *These disturbances are often perceived by the person as sudden and independent interventions in their usual way of responding or functioning.*

Hearing voices, depersonalization, derealization, "constituted" ideas, "made" wishes, "made" desires, "made" feelings, and "done" actions are the most typical manifestations of dissociative

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interventions. Other manifestations include depersonalization and derealization. (p. xxi) According to Howell (2005), dissociative processes can occur in a variety of ways, most of which are not problematic. Specifically, Dell (2009d) argued that spontaneous, survival-related divergence is part of a normal, evolutionarily selected, species-specific response. This decomposition is automatic and reflexive and is part of a short, time-limited, normal biological reaction that subsides as soon as the danger is removed. It is not yet possible to have an adequate understanding of the link that exists between this dissociative response and the level and type of dissociation that is characteristic of dissociative disorders.

7. Conceptual Challenges and Physiological Manifestations Associated with Alternative Identities

The individual suffering from dissociative identity disorder is a single individual who has a sense of being composed of several distinct identities that can psychologically function independently of one another. These subjective identities may, at different moments, either assume executive control over one's body and behavior, or may influence one's experience and behavior "from the inside". Both events can happen at the same time. Taken as a whole, the individual with DID has a personality or identity that is made up of all their many disguises or other identities. There are many ways to characterize an alternative concept of identity. As an example, Putnam (1989) defined them as "very different states of consciousness structured around a predominant emotion, sense of self (including body image), a limited repertoire of activities, and memories attached to a range of situations". According to RP Kluft (1988b), a discrete self-state (also known as personality) is the mental address of a stable and persistent pattern of selective mobilization of mental contents and functions. This model of selective mobilization of mental contents and functions is behaviorally invigorable with significant role-playing and role-playing dimensions and is sensitive to intrapsychic, interpersonal, and environmental stimuli.

As well as having basic psychodynamic components, it is structured within and linked to a highly consistent neuropsychophysiological model of activation. It acts as a receiver, processor and

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storage center for feelings, experiences and processing of earlier events and ideas and/or what is present and expected. It also works as a hub for predicting future events . He can start mental processes and activities, as well as to have his own identity and the ability to think for himself.

There are several words formed to describe the subjective. A sense of self-states or identities that a DID patient may experience. Personality, personality state, self-state, differentiated self-state, change, personality change, alternative identity, part of mind, part of mind, part of self, dissociative part of personality, and being are some of the terms that fall under (see Van der Hart & Dorahy, 2009) .

Since DSM–IV–TR (American Psychiatric Association, 2000a) uses the term alternative identity, this word is also used in the Guide. Clinicians need to pay attention to the specific and personal language they use when describing the other identities of their patients with dissociative identity disorder. Patients often describe themselves as consisting of a variety of elements, including but not limited to:

- *Parts, interiors, aspects, sides, forms of existence, sounds, floors, self, age, people, persons, individuals, spirits, demons, and others.*

If the use of these terms is inconsistent with therapeutic recommendations and/or the clinician believes that certain terms will reinforce the belief that alternative identities are separate people or persons rather than a single person with subjectively split-self aspects, then it may be helpful to use terms used by patients to describe their identities. However, this is only true if the use of these terms is not in line with therapeutic recommendations. Severe and prolonged traumatic experiences can lead to the development of different, personalized behavioral states (ie, primitive alternative identities) in the child. This has the effect of having intolerable traumatic memories, effects, sensations, beliefs, or behaviors and mitigating their effects on the child's overall development. The secondary construction of these different behavioral states takes place over time through a series of developmental and symbolic processes that result in the characteristics of certain alternative identities. As the child progresses through privacy, adolescence, and adulthood,

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identities may expand in number, become more complex, and gain a sense of being different from one another (RP Kluft, 1984; Putnam, 1997).

The development of dissociative identity disorder (DID) occurs during childhood, and clinicians rarely meet cases of DID caused by adult-onset trauma (unless superimposed on pre-existing childhood trauma and pre-existing latent or dormant disintegration).

Another etiological model proposes that the development of dissociative identity disorder (DID) is dependent on the coexistence of the following four factors:

- (a) *Dissociation ability.*
- (b) *Experiences that exceed the child's non-dissociative coping ability.*
- (c) *construction of DID alternative identities with individualized characteristics such as names, ages, and genders ; and*
- (d) *Lack of isolating or soothing and restorative experiences for the child (RP Kluft, 1984).*

It is possible that the secondary structure of alternative identities may differ slightly among patients. As a result, therapists skilled in the treatment of dissociative identity disorder often pay little attention to the overt style and presentation of the many other identities their patients display. Instead, they focus their attention on the cognitive, emotional, and psychodynamic features that each identity embodies, while simultaneously addressing identities as a system of representation, symbolization, and meaning. Another etiological model, based on Janet's concepts and called "structural dissociation of personality," is an effort to develop a unified dissociation explanation that includes DID. This hypothesis is based on the ideas of Janet (Van der Hart et al., 2006). According to this school of thought, dissociation is the result of a person's fundamental inability to integrate personality functions and intellectual systems. After experiencing potentially traumatic events, the personality system has the potential to split into a "seemingly normal part of the personality", committed to daily functioning, and an "emotional part of the personality". Both sections are devoted to protecting the individual. Not to be confused with the psychodynamic concept of defense, the term "defense" in this sense refers to psychobiological processes of survival

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in response to a vital danger, such as fight or flight. It has been hypothesized that prolonged exposure to traumatic experiences or neglect may cause secondary structural dissociation, which may lead to the development of extra emotional aspects of one's personality. In summary, these developmental hypotheses assume that dissociative identity disorder does not result from a pre-developed, unified mind or "core personality" that breaks down or disintegrates after reaching maturity.

the result of failure of normal developmental integration during critical early developmental periods brought on by overwhelming experiences and disturbing caregiver-child interactions (including neglect and unresponsiveness). This, in turn, causes some traumatized children to develop different, personalized behavioral states, which over time eventually evolve into alternative identities associated with IPD. Some authors argue that clinicians who have a strong belief in dissociative identity disorder (DID) and who implicitly or explicitly influence patients to express their IPD symptoms manage the disorder. IPD is a socially constructed condition resulting from therapist cues (e.g., suggestive questioning about the existence of practical alternative personalities), media influences (e.g., film and television depictions of DID), and broader sociocultural expectations about putative clinical characteristics. According to this "sociocognitive" model of DID. For example, some proponents of the sociocognitive model believe that the publication of the book *Sybil* and the release of the movie *Sybil* in the 1970s played a key role in shaping notions of DID in the minds of the public as well as psychotherapists. Despite these reasons, there are no real studies showing that the complex phenomenology of DID can be created through suggestion, transmission, or hypnosis. Not only that, but there is also no evidence to suggest that this could happen (DW Brown, Frischholz, & Schefflin, 1999; Gleaves, 1996; Loewenstein, 2007).

trauma model of DID has several advantages over the sociocognitive model, supported by various evidence. These include studies showing DID in children, adolescents, and adults with proven maltreatment and evidence that DID symptoms precede any interaction with clinicians (Hornstein & Putnam, 1992; Lewis, Yeager, Swica, Pincus & Lewis, 1997), psychophysiology studies . And there are studies on the discriminant validity of dissociative disorders using psychobiology as

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described above, as well as structured interview protocols. There are also many other studies showing DID. In addition, naturalistic studies have shown that people with dissociative identity disorder (DID) describe a wide variety of symptoms previously unknown to patients, the public, and even most physicians, according to research data that defines IPD (Dell, 2006). It is important for clinicians to keep in mind that some patients with DID are unaware or self-aware that their inner experiences are different from those of other people.

of other identities and other dissociative symptoms is often dismissed and denied by people with dissociative identity disorder (DID); this is consistent with the theory that dissociation can serve as a defense mechanism against unpleasant reality. This form of denial is consistent with the defensive function of rejecting both the traumatic experience and the emotions associated with it, as well as the later dissociated sense of self. It should come as no surprise that people with dissociative identity disorder typically display symptoms of burnout and depression alongside avoidant personality disorder (see Cardea & Spiegel, 1996). Every case of dissociative identity disorder is associated with a significant traumatic event in the person's past, most of which occurred during childhood (Putnam, 1997; Putnam, Guroff, Silberman, Barban, & Post, 1986).

8. Conclusion

Consequently, the diagnostic process should include an effort to evaluate the patient's earlier trauma experiences. However, clinicians should exercise careful clinical judgment when deciding how aggressively to pursue details of traumatic experiences during first interviews. This is especially important when details of traumatic experiences are poorly or incompletely remembered, or when remembering or describing the trauma exceeds the person's emotional abilities. Asking about a person's traumatic past too soon can cause them to experience a lack of ostentatious compensation (ie, severe post- traumatic and dissociative symptoms). Early in treatment, DID patients often present a fragmented and inconsistent history because of their dissociative amnesia; however, a more complete personal history will typically appear over the course of treatment. DDNOS Diagnosis of dissociative disorders not otherwise specified

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(DDNOS) is given to a considerable proportion of dissociative cases seen in clinical settings. The DSM–IV–TR supplies a correct description of a considerable number of these DDNOS cases. An example of DDNOS is "Clinical presentations similar to dissociative identity disorder that do not meet all criteria for this disorder" (American Psychiatric Association, 2000a, p. 532). There seem to be two main categories of these DDNOS-1 cases:

- (a) *Full-blown DID cases whose diagnosis has not yet been confirmed (through the overt manifestation of alternative identities), and*
- (b) *with some internal fragmentation and/or rare amnesia events. Both categories can be subcategorized (Dell, 2009b). DDNOS-1 patients typically suffer DID-like interruptions in their functioning due to transitions in self-states and the entry of emotions and memories into consciousness. Patients in the second group of DDNOS-1 are considered "near-DID".*

the above-mentioned phenomena are typically more subtle than ostentatious DID specimens. It is important to have a higher level of skills and ability to recognize their assets. In terms of treatment, however, the view of most experts is that cases of DDNOS-1 – yet undiagnosed DID or DID – benefit from many treatments designed for DID.

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